

Discussion: Is Runet the Last Adaptation Tool?

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One of the most singular impressions I have experienced when attending international conferences focussing on the Russian segment of the Internet—most recently, at *Russia Online: The Russian-Language Blogosphere and Participatory Internet*, a 2008 conference hosted by the Harriman Institute and the School of Journalism at Columbia University and the Berkman Center for Internet & Society at Harvard University—is a certain dissonance concerning the choice of research fields that European and American researchers make in comparison with their Russian counterparts. Private conversations with a number of individuals who are extremely active on the Russian Internet scene, either as practitioners or as researchers (such as Anton Nossik, Masha Gessen, and Anna Kachkaeva among others), confirm that they have experienced the same feeling and have tried to understand the motivations causing this dissonance. This contribution will provide my interpretation of the issue, and hopefully will attract meaningful feedback from other researchers in Russia and abroad.

American and European researchers have a keen interest in the Russian networked public sphere (see, for instance, Kuchins 2007; Alexander 2004; Schmidt and Teubener 2006 and 2007). Some are inspired by the belief that modern communications can support press freedom and establish new bonds of cooperation between people, ultimately facilitating the creation of grassroots movements and the mobilisation of broad and diverse offline groups into civil and political action. Others test this hypothesis by exploring the cultural background of Runet. Many a Russian colleague I know have informed that they are often frustrated by what they regard, only half jokingly, as an “obsession” with politics.

The interest in online engagement is considered at best naïve and/or narrow, since it is seen as holding back serious analyses of more subtle social and cultural developments. At times the wish to examine the political and participatory outlook of Runet is also viewed as a by-product of a dominating American and/or British approach, which aims to impose a biased approach on the study of all things Russian, an approach that has little to do with Russia’s real and diverse developments, and which mainly leads to judgemental and confrontational conclusions.

Russian Internet experts, meanwhile, have been keen in the last few years to focus on the quantitative aspects of Internet penetration and on technological and business issues. As their main platform they use Internet conferences, which, in turn, have become very important events for the Internet community (for instance, annual conferences C-IB [КИБ] on Internet

and Business and the Russian Internet Forum have been held regularly since 1997). Such strategy is quite understandable in the light of the recent Russian Internet boom that has generated significant business growth, facilitating the transformation of smart practitioners into successful entrepreneurs. On the opposite side of the spectrum, many researchers have been keen to focus on specialised issues concerning literature and the cultural discourse on the Web, following the celebrated Russian cultural and intellectual tradition. The best example is the Russian State University for the Humanities that in December 2006 organised a conference on literature and reading on the Internet, the event has been mimicked by other Russian universities, all relying on the support of the Federal Agency on the Press and Mass Communications.

A comprehensive assessment of content available in the Russian segment of the Internet, including an analysis of online civic and political engagement is, to my knowledge, noticeably lacking. In 2007, presenting a Moscow State University publication on global Internet development and interactive electronic media in Russia, Ivan Zassursky, director of the Laboratory for Media Culture and Communications of the Journalism Faculty, wrote: “The lack of scientific literature and sources remains a problem. There are very few serious works available in Russian.” The second part of the publication, researching the Russian blogosphere, examines the social, cultural and media aspects of blogging, but when it turns to Russian concerns, it actually leaves aside the examination of political aspects. In conversations with Russian Internet practitioners and research colleagues I have sometimes had the feeling that many are unwilling to look at the “big picture” and to tackle political issues pertinent to their own country’s future. At the same time the Russian practitioners who are actually interested and personally engaged in the life of civil movements present in the Russian blogosphere appear somehow over-optimistic on the real—as opposed to virtual—outcome of Runet’s potential for grassroots social-networking initiatives. The following two cases exemplify my argument.

At the Columbia University 2008 conference, Internet expert and respected practitioner Sergei Kuznetsov, who is personally engaged in a number of worthy charitable and cultural initiatives, alongside his principal online content-producing entrepreneurial activity, spoke at length about the value of Runet initiatives and projects that have produced excellent engagement results online. While sharing Kuznetsov’s enthusiasm to a large extent, I and other participants to the symposium pointed out at the fact that only a tiny number of initiatives carrying a potentially political angle could be considered consistent or successful in the offline world, and that an accurate assessment would be most valuable.

Another conference participant, Olessia Koltsova, from the Higher School of Economics, St. Petersburg campus, presented her research on the online and offline activity surrounding last year’s attempts to prevent the closing of the European University in St. Petersburg. Koltsova’s conclusion was that the online activism of students, scholars and supporters of the highly respected university in Russia and abroad had indeed been very extremely significant and visible. However, she said that it was impossible to assess the extent of the importance of online activism in the decision-making process that eventually spared the university, because of the total lack of political transparency on the issue.

My aim is to offer my reading of the cultural and sociological background that I take into consideration when I examine Russian online activity. I will base my argument on the in-

sightful points of view expressed by several Russian scholars, and also on the results of a recent research on the political influence and practice of the Russian Internet, which I conducted with other colleagues for the Reuters Institute for the Study of Journalism at Oxford University.

Institutes versus an Alternative Social Universe

In an interview related to this research, sociologist Boris Dubin argued that the hopes of those who expect Internet civil society activities in Russia to increase quickly and have a significant impact on the offline world seem quite naive. Since the Internet is essentially a horizontal communication network, he argued, a corresponding vertical network of existing institutes (whose functions are sometimes obstructed, but whose existence is nonetheless respected by society and by the political leadership) would be needed for the creation of ideas that could successfully translate into offline activity and mobilisation.

The discussion around the importance of institutes is not new, and remains one of the most important keys to understanding a situation that seems to develop by endlessly reproducing itself. One very interesting contribution to the discussion was made by Irina Prokhorova, the editor of the *New Literary Review*; she offered her explanation accurately reflecting the view of most Russian academic and intellectual circles in “Heirs to the Underground, or What Keeps Russian Culture Going,” published by *Kultura* in October 2005. Replying to the complaint of a Western colleague, who lamented that “It’s impossible to work in Russia—there are so many brilliant personalities, but no institutions at all.” Prokhorova explained:

What is peculiar about Russia is not the absence of institutions as such, but rather a fatal discrepancy between those institutions and the functions they were created to fulfil...The most important result of this social deformation has been a spontaneous evolution of informal, parallel infrastructures of social life in Russia, which usually remain in the shadow of public attention and are therefore difficult to access for outsiders.
(Prokhorova 2005).

This situation, Prokhorova argues, has clearly created a “cultural duality,” one of the consequences of which has been the strengthening of Russian literature as a social institution. As we know this concept reflects on the emergence and consolidation of a strong and varied Russian underground movement between the 1950s until the 1980s. Prokhorova emphasizes the notion that the underground movement should not be seen as a unified group in opposition to Soviet totalitarianism (a rather dominating point of view until recently in the US and Europe) but rather as “an alternative social universe with its own creative associations and circles, its own authorities and aesthetic criteria, its own press, an efficient distribution system for its political and artistic production, its own literary prizes, a social life with its own peculiar rituals, its own foreign contacts” (Prokhorova 2005).

The feeling that this description corresponds quite neatly to the model of the Russian Internet is reinforced by Prokhorova’s testimony that this style of social behaviour characteristic of the underground movement, and celebrating a narrow circle of friends, continued, and

in many new professional ways developed, in the 1990s and remains valid to this day. Prokhorova purposely relates to the “Internet boom, which spawned a plethora of virtual projects.” She then singled out the economic crisis of 1998, which triggered a shift of political priorities, setting off mechanisms that she defined “of partial re-Sovietisation.” She specifically identified the restoration process set in motion after the crisis, targeting the weak socio-cultural institutions of the late and post-Soviet periods, “in an attempt to concentrate all means of influencing public opinion in the hands of the state.”

It is precisely as a response to these developments that Prokhorova sees the role of the Internet. The new medium, transforming from its pioneering age of self-made and naïve websites, gave way in Russia and elsewhere to web-based platforms with endless networking possibilities. The natural *modus vivendi* of these networks in Russia is aimed, in Prokhorova’s view, at preserving and restructuring the system of cultural initiatives that had supported the existence of an alternative social universe in Soviet times and that had been legitimised, albeit on a very shaky base, in the first post-Soviet decade. It is here, she says, in this alternative social universe, that heated political debates and fully-fledged literary disputes take place. As researchers of the Russian Internet have noticed, debates and disputes are indeed intense and at times fierce, but they are far from mobilising long-lasting forms of activism, particularly activism with tangible social and political repercussions offline.

Should these repercussions be relevant for Russian Internet users involved in a vibrant and varied alternative social reality? My discussions with a large number of Russian Internet users and experts indicate that in their view researchers looking for signs of political activism seem to repeat the same pattern of their colleagues who, in Soviet times, regarded the underground movement without differentiation, imagining it united in its opposition to Soviet totalitarianism. In so doing researchers are seen as brushing aside the important fact that while a handful of activists were undeniably committed to that cause, ready to risk bravely their own life and freedom, the vast majority of the Soviet underground movement was motivated by the very natural urge to express various personal, artistic and cultural views publicly, and ultimately to have fun amid the grim Soviet reality.

Defence and Adaptation

One can easily notice a sense of genuine surprise in discussions among Internet practitioners and researchers. For instance, following a discussion on online engagement and participatory Internet in Russia (October 2008), one of the participants posted the following comment in his LiveJournal blog:

Participants were engaged and the discussion was interesting. I was, however, rather surprised by the serious approach of some [participants] towards civil activism...In Russia this kind of engagement has a real effect only when it is supported by other activities carried out among personal connections in the so-called corridors of power (Drugoi 2008).

The author of this comment is Rustem Adagamov, whose online identity is Drugoi. Adagamov’s interesting photoblog has been consistently one of the leaders of the Russian blogosphere and the unchallenged leader of LiveJournal in 2008. According to Yandex, Russia’s

main search engine, the blog had 198,644 hits on January 7, 2009 and had enjoyed roughly the same popularity index throughout last year. Adagamov's assessment was that, if unsupported by informal ties with powerful decision-makers, "no online petition and no mobilisation carried out in online communities and street actions" can achieve tangible results in the offline reality.

A generally defensive and distrustful connotation of Internet use, often masked by a layer of cynicism, is widespread among Russian users. One of their primary concerns is the need to preserve the existence of an alternative social universe, taking advantage of modern technological developments. If substantiated through comprehensive empirical research, this trend would indicate that the Internet has also assumed the role of the tool of adaptation to a political reality that users see outside the reach of their real personal and collective influence. At the moment this hypothesis seems to be substantiated by the results of public opinion research. Levada Centre polls, for instance, show that 72 percent of Russians in 2007 said they had no way to influence the state decision-making process and 80 percent believed they were not in the condition to participate in the political and economic life of the country. In this respect Internet users are in tune with the majority of the population. Russian sociologists affirm that it is precisely strategies of adaptation, together with distrust for every institute of civil society, with the notable exclusion of the presidency, that are responsible for the lack of widespread civil activity aimed at change on and offline. Dubin describes post-Soviet Russia as an "adapting society" (Dubin 2008). He conceptualises adaptation in terms of "passive and mainly reactive (in a stimulus-reaction mode) behaviour of most social groups." Dubin notes that the definition relates to behaviour.

Depending on the centralized power, on a social and political order imposed by this power and accepted by the population, as opposed to citizens' assertion of own individual and group interest or to a vigorous activity aimed at changing the balance of social forces (Dubin 2008).

In Dubin's view, this behaviour is determined by the habit and by the fear of losing perceived securities. It has a profound influence on attitudes, ultimately resulting in different forms of criticism of other people's activity and success. Widespread forms of disapproval are in turn fertile soil for negative and generally cynical approaches toward "the other" and strictly limit the emergence of attitudes of positive solidarity for anyone outside one's immediate circle of family and like-minded individuals. Equally importantly, the adaptation mode is seen by Dubin as one of the main causes of the fragmentation of civil activity and the atomisation of society.

Dubin correlates directly these reactive and fragmentary tendencies to defensive connotations that allow the preservation of an alternative social universe. The correlation, essential for the study of Internet engagement and mobilisation, is entrenched in the conviction that any social form and social initiative can be manipulated by the state. At the same time it reveals deep and widespread distrust for any social institute, with the notable exception of the presidency. According to Levada-Centre data in the last years the feeling of vulnerability and individual weakness vis-à-vis the law and the very institutes in charge of implementing its

letter (from courts to prosecutors and police organs) has been growing among Russians and is currently shared by more than two-thirds of the population.

Another Russian sociologist and culturologist, Daniil Dondurei, in a recent article lamented that

The huge amount of contrasting interpretations of events of the last two decades seems to have confused many people. According to recent polls some three-fourths of Russians think of themselves as happy, roughly the same amount approve the official stance on South-Ossetia and Abkhazia, but at the same time do not trust any official, except the president and the prime minister. Despite the fact that private property is widespread and legal, most people continue to rely mostly on the state. At the same time, 78 percent of businessmen, when involved in commercial disputes, say they prefer to avoid court decisions because they do not believe in the fairness of judges. Such eclecticism is not fortuitous. Thanks to the intensive and assiduous work of the Russian political, economic and media elite aimed at creating mass perceptions, a steady sense of deception toward the results of modernization has been established in the public's opinion" (Dondurei 2008).

Dondurei appears to sustain Dubin's argument concerning adaptation and its dangers when he asks:

How are we going to fight legal nihilism when the public's psychology has adapted perfectly? Six out of ten citizens acknowledge that they have a more or less tolerant attitude towards corruption. Some of them believe that it is actually corruption that allows the complex system of Russian life to move" (Dondurei 2008).

Far from making judgemental conclusions vis-à-vis different scholarly approaches to Internet research, this article intends to serve as a call for more research projects on different aspects of Internet use, in particular on the Internet as a tool of adaptation with the goal of preserving an alternative social universe and on the strategies adopted by different actors, for example, by different communities as well as manipulative groups often linked to the state, to achieve their goals.

The Reuters Institute's pilot project concluded that in the Russian context, at present at least, new communications developments are not breaking down well-established patterns of power. The state remains the main mobilising agent. Following a few years of spontaneous—and inexpensive—"anarchy," Runet currently does operate as a device to spread and share information, but largely among closed clusters of like-minded users who are seldom able or willing to cooperate. However, it does operate as a platform which the state uses successfully to consolidate its power. The activists are rendered at best only partly effective by their limited public and political skills, difficulty in fostering productive discussion among themselves, and inability to overcome the widespread lack of trust among users.

Our pilot research confirmed Dubin's view that currently Runet is restricted to the status of "a device to test one's own circle" and can be used to reproduce mechanisms of propaganda and manipulation well tested offline. Further multi disciplinary studies that would link the use of the Russian Internet for literary expression—including such interesting developments as the widespread language of *padonki* and its use for manipulation and verbal bully-

ing, as well as the strategies explaining how information technologies are shaped by the social context in which they are deployed are much needed. Olga Goriunova, in her interesting account of the language of *padonki* examined against the traditional Russian intelligentsia “talk,” notes that the “shared notion, accepted by many, that defence and protest can only but be passive” and makes the link with Jean Baudrillard’s analysis of the gradual disappearance of the traditional political struggle and its practices in Western Europe (Baudrillard 2002). Goriunova, however, does not examine in depth the possibility of use of the *padonki* language for manipulation and verbal bullying, particularly during pre-electoral Runet debates (Goriunova 2006).

In a United Nations report examining the emergence of new telecommunication technologies in the late years of the Soviet Union and in the early post-Soviet era, Rafal Rahozinski noted that “what is the most interesting about the Internet’s emergence in Russia is not the way in which technology transformed society, but rather the way in which society colonised the technology” (Rahozinski 1999). The report was issued in 1999 and it would be extremely valuable to see whether Rahozinski’s conclusion can still be considered relevant.

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